

Spatial discontinuous Galerkin spectral element method for a family of chromatography models in CADET

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Abstract

Packed bed liquid chromatography is widely applied in academia and industry. Model-based methods are increasingly utilized for process development and optimization, demanding multitudes of complex simulations. We derive spatial arbitrary order discontinuous Galerkin (DG) discretizations for three commonly used chromatography models, including the general rate model (GRM). The methods are integrated in the open source CADET software, making efficient implementations publicly available for the first time. The DG CADET code is validated and benchmarked against the original finite volume CADET code. We observe great performance advantages for DG, depending on the discrete problem size. For a four-component steric mass action GRM, we achieve a speed-up of an order of magnitude for an error range typical for engineering applications. We explore the performance of a collocation Legendre-Gauß-Lobatto (LGL) quadrature DG method in com-

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parison to an exact integration DG method. Our performance benchmarks indicate a slight advantage for collocation DG.

Keywords: Column liquid chromatography, general rate model, lumped rate model with pores, lumped rate model without pores, discontinuous Galerkin spectral element method, CADET

1. Introduction

1.1. Problem Description and Relevance

Chromatography’s modern process development and optimization is increasingly advanced by in-depth understanding of the underlying mechanisms. First principles modeling is thus fundamentally tied to problem description and disentanglement of cause and effect. The insights gained can inform the development of new chromatography materials and techniques, leading to improved separations, better product quality, and increased productivity. Overall, mechanistic modeling is a crucial driver of innovation and optimization in industry and scientific research.

A variety of chromatographic models has been developed, which describe the movement of molecules through the column, as well as the interaction between molecules of the solid and liquid phases. Different levels of detail are used to describe both of these aspects, and binding models can accommodate diverse adsorption mechanisms. The general rate model (GRM), the lumped rate model with pores (LRMP), the lumped rate model without pores (LRM) and the ideal model (IM) are the most prominent transport models in literature, with the GRM being the most comprehensive of these (see e.g. Gu, 2015; Guiochon et al., 2006; Schmidt-Traub et al., 2020, partly using different

20 names). Each of these transport models is described by a system of partial
21 differential equations (PDE) in time and space and is complemented by a
22 binding model, generally resulting in an overall system of partial differential
23 algebraic equations (PDAE).

24 Since no closed-form solutions are known for most of these chromatogra-
25 phy models, numerical approximations of the spatio-temporal development
26 of solute concentration profiles are required. As there is no universally best
27 suited model, it is crucial to have a simulation tool that provides a selection
28 of models with varying complexity to fit the individual needs of any appli-
29 cation. With more complex models and a multitude of simulations required
30 in parameter estimation algorithms (see e.g. Heymann et al., 2022; Forssén
31 et al., 2006; Hahn et al., 2014), process design and optimization (see e.g.
32 Kozorog et al., 2023; Schmölder and Kaspereit, 2020), uncertainty quantifi-
33 cation (see e.g. Zhang et al., 2017), model-based scale-up/down (see e.g. Gu,
34 2015), and real-time monitoring (see e.g. Vilas and Vande Wouwer, 2011;
35 Erdem et al., 2004), computationally efficient solvers are of particular im-
36 portance. Even with modern hard- and software, these applications require
37 considerable compute times up to several hours, days and weeks. On the
38 other hand, new processes need to be developed within a short time frame,
39 e.g., in the pharmaceutical industry where production is steadily expanded
40 by new molecules and stationary phases (Kumar and Lenhoff, 2020).

41 *1.2. Numerical Algorithms and Simulation Software*

42 In numerical simulation of chromatographic models, the method of lines,
43 i.e. the separation of spatial and temporal discretization, has prevailed.
44 That is, the model PDAE are spatially discretized to yield coupled systems

45 of differential-algebraic equations (DAE), which in turn are discretized in
46 time, which for implicit methods leads to (nonlinear) algebraic systems to
47 be solved. Since highly optimized DAE and algebraic solvers are publicly
48 available, these problems can be solved independently by well-established
49 algorithms. Multiple spatial discretization methods have been applied in
50 chromatography, including variations of finite differences (FD), finite vol-
51 ume (FV) and finite elements (FE) schemes. First order methods require
52 comparably fine discretizations to yield accurate approximations and are
53 therefore computationally demanding. On the other hand, linear high order
54 (≥ 2) methods are naturally non-monotone, which is known as Godunov's or-
55 der barrier theorem (Godunov and Bohachevsky, 1959). That is, these meth-
56 ods suffer from unphysical oscillations near discontinuities, known as Gibbs
57 phenomenon (Jerri, 1998; Gottlieb and Shu, 1997). This problem can either
58 be addressed by nonlinear mechanisms such as flux limiters or (weighted)
59 essentially non oscillatory (ENO) high order schemes, or be avoided for dis-
60 persive equations by employing a sufficiently fine spatial resolution at the
61 expense of computational cost.

62 FD methods are naturally mass dissipative which can be reduced with
63 grid refinement and higher order FD schemes. There are mimetic FD schemes
64 that secure mass conservation but rely on more complex theory and imple-
65 mentation (Lipnikov et al., 2014). Higher order essentially non-oscillatory
66 FD schemes were presented, e.g., by Alhumaizi (2004). Since mass dissipa-
67 tion is profoundly unphysical, naturally mass conserving methods, such as
68 FV or specific FE schemes, are often preferred.

69 As higher order FV schemes rely on information from multiple neigh-

70 bouring discrete points, these schemes face difficulties with higher order re-
71 constructions at domain boundaries. Compared to (classical) continuous FE
72 schemes, the discontinuous Galerkin spectral method (DGSEM) introduces
73 additional artificial dispersion, which is often considered beneficial due to its
74 stabilizing effect (Brezzi et al., 2006). Moreover, the DGSEM yields a local
75 scheme, i.e. the element-wise computations only depend on adjacent ele-
76 ments. Thus, boundary conditions can be naturally applied to such schemes
77 while retaining their (high) order.

78 Several open source and commercial software packages have been devel-
79 oped using various numerical approaches, some of the more recent and more
80 popular are given in the following:

- 81 • STLC (Andersson et al., 2023): Applies a FE orthogonal collocation
82 spatial method (arbitrary order) with single elements for the GRM
83 particle discretization and a temporal implicit backward Euler scheme
84 (first order) and is publicly available as open source code.
- 85 • VERSE LC (Berninger et al., 1991): Employs spatial FE orthogonal
86 collocation (arbitrary order) with single elements for the GRM particle
87 discretization, and uses an implicit backwards differentiation formula
88 (BDF) of fifth order. Commercial software.
- 89 • Chromulator-IEX (Gu, 2015): Uses quadratic FE and a orthogonal
90 collocation method for the GRM particle discretization (third order),
91 which is complemented by a fifth order implicit BDF temporal method.
92 Commercial software.
- 93 • GoSilico™ Chromatography Modeling Software (formerly known as ChromX,

94 Hahn et al. (2015)): Employs spatial quadratic FE (third order) with
95 optional streamline-upwind-Petrov-Galerkin stabilization to suppress
96 oscillations. The scheme is completed using an implicit Crank-Nicolson
97 temporal method (second order), but other time integration methods
98 are also available. Commercial software.

- 99 • ChromWorks (YpsoFacto): Unknown numerical methods. Commercial
100 software.
- 101 • ChromaTech (Meyer et al., 2020): Uses a combination of DGSEM and
102 Galerkin spectral method (GSM) for spatial discretization, comple-
103 mented by an implicit adaptive time-step BDF temporal method (up
104 to fifth order) and is a commercial software.
- 105 • CADET version 4 (Leweke and von Lieres, 2016): Applies a weighted
106 essentially non oscillatory (WENO) FV spatial method (globally second
107 order, von Lieres and Andersson, 2010) which is complemented by an
108 implicit adaptive time-step BDF temporal method (up to fifth order)
109 and is publicly available as open source code.
- 110 • CADET version 5 (this work): Employs a spatial (collocation) DGSEM
111 for the interstitial volume and an (exact integration) DGSEM for the
112 particle discretization (both arbitrary order) which are complemented
113 by an implicit adaptive time-step BDF temporal method (up to fifth
114 order) and is publicly available as open source code.

115 Meyer et al. (2020) showed that arbitrary order discontinuous Galerkin
116 (DG) methods can achieve substantial computational advantages compared

117 to the CADET FV implementation. Interestingly, no mechanism to pre-
118 vent oscillations was built into the spatial method. Arguably, the dispersive
119 terms in the chromatographic model equations prevented the occurrence of
120 discontinuities and steep gradients for the considered settings.

121 Due to their high theoretical convergence order and thus superior perfor-
122 mance, we have extended CADET by spatial arbitrary order DG discretiza-
123 tions to simulate the GRM, LRMP and LRM, making them publicly available
124 to the chromatography community for the first time. We optionally employ
125 an exact integration DGSEM and a collocation DGSEM to discretize the
126 interstitial volume mass balance, and an exact integration DGSEM to dis-
127 cretize the particle mass balance. This extends the work of Meyer et al.
128 (2020), where the GSM in the particles only employs one element and is
129 thus more affected by stability issues and oscillations, which the authors
130 deemed less relevant since there are no advective terms causing instability.
131 Nonetheless the occurrence and magnitude of steep concentration gradients
132 or self-sharpening fronts inside the particles strongly depends on the specific
133 binding behavior and might cause stability issues. Our DGSEM on the other
134 hand allows to employ non-equidistant multiple elements. This has a stabi-
135 lizing effect that can be beneficial for specific settings, and allows a targeted
136 resolution of the particles. Additionally, we include core-shell particles that
137 employ impenetrable particle cores (see e.g. Hayes et al., 2014).

138 The collocation DGSEM for the interstitial volume discretization is an
139 approach to further improve performance compared to the exact integration
140 DGSEM, which was also used by Meyer et al. (2020). Contrary to exact inte-
141 gration DGSEM, collocated schemes perform inexact numerical integration,

142 which results in a diagonal mass matrix instead of a dense one.

143 We benchmark our new implementations against the FV scheme of CADET.
144 We pay particular attention to the occurrence of oscillations and unphysical
145 negative concentrations and their impact on performance compared to the
146 WENO FV scheme.

147 2. Models

148 The modular framework of CADET allows any implemented transport
149 and binding model to be combined. To avoid repetition, since the discretiza-
150 tions of the transport models are quite similar, we consider here only the
151 GRM with surface diffusion and a rapid-equilibrium steric mass action (SMA)
152 model binding. In the evaluation however, we verify and benchmark our code
153 for the GRM, LRMP and LRM and additionally consider the well-known lin-
154 ear and Langmuir binding models (see e.g. Guiochon et al. (2006)).

155 2.1. Transport Model

156 We anticipate that the GRM introduced here takes into account particle-
157 type distributions (PSD, see e.g. Gritti et al., 2011) and core-shell particles
158 (see e.g. Hayes et al., 2014) in addition to its formulation in the standard
159 literature.

160 In liquid column chromatography, a cylindrical column of length $L > 0$
161 is packed with a fixed bed of spherical particles with porosity $\varepsilon_c \in (0, 1)$.
162 The continuous PSD is discretized by N_p particle types with respective outer
163 radii $R_{p,j} > 0$ and inner radii $R_{c,j} \geq 0$ for each particle type $j \in \{1, \dots, N_p\}$.

164 The corresponding volume fractions $d_j \in (0, 1]$ are required to satisfy

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N_p} d_j = 1 \quad \forall z \in (0, L), \quad (1)$$

165 and optionally depend on the axial position, i.e. $d_j: (0, L) \mapsto (0, 1]$. The
 166 particles are porous themselves, forming a particle volume with porosity
 167 $\varepsilon_{p,j} \in (0, 1)$, which leads to a total porosity of $\varepsilon_t := \varepsilon_c + (1 - \varepsilon_c) \sum_{j=0}^{N_p} d_j \varepsilon_{p,j}$.
 168 A mobile phase mixture comprising solute molecule species $i \in \{1, \dots, N_c\}$
 169 is pumped through the column with an interstitial velocity $u > 0$. The bulk
 170 concentrations $c_i^b(z, t)$ in the interstitial volume are assumed to be homoge-
 171 neous over column cross-sections, i.e. they are only functions of the axial
 172 position $z \in [0, L]$ and simulation time $t \in [0, T_{\text{end}}]$. Concentrations inside
 173 the particles are assumed to be spherically symmetric, i.e. respective mobile
 174 and stationary phase concentrations $c_{i,j}^p(z, r, t)$ and $c_{i,j}^s(z, r, t)$ are addition-
 175 ally functions of the radial position $r \in [R_{c,j}, R_{p,j}]$ within the particle.

176 In the interstitial column volume, mass transfer is governed by the convection-
 177 diffusion-reaction equation

$$\varepsilon_c \frac{\partial c_i^b}{\partial t} = -\varepsilon_c u \frac{\partial c_i^b}{\partial z} + \varepsilon_c D_{\text{ax},i} \frac{\partial^2 c_i^b}{\partial z^2} - (1 - \varepsilon_c) \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \frac{3d_j}{R_{p,j}} k_{f,i,j} \left(c_i^b - c_{i,j}^p \Big|_{r=R_{p,j}} \right) \quad (2)$$

178 in $(0, T_{\text{end}}) \times (0, L)$ with Danckwerts boundary conditions

$$u c_{\text{in},i} = \left(u c_i^b - D_{\text{ax},i} \frac{\partial c_i^b}{\partial z} \right) \Big|_{z=0} \quad \text{on } (0, T_{\text{end}}), \quad (3a)$$

$$0 = -D_{\text{ax},i} \frac{\partial c_i^b}{\partial z} \Big|_{z=L} \quad \text{on } (0, T_{\text{end}}). \quad (3b)$$

179 The axial dispersion coefficient is denoted by D_{ax} , and $k_{f,i,j}$ is the film mass
 180 transfer coefficient, and $c_{\text{in},i}$ denotes the column inlet concentration for each
 181 component.

182 The initial conditions at $t = 0$ are given by

$$c_i^b \Big|_{t=0} = c_{\text{init},i}^b \quad \text{in } (0, L). \quad (4)$$

183 In the particles, diffusion-reaction equations hold in $(0, T_{\text{end}}] \times (0, L) \times$
 184 $(R_{c,j}, R_{p,j})$:

$$\frac{\partial c_{i,j}^p}{\partial t} + \frac{(1 - \varepsilon_{p,j})}{\varepsilon_{p,j}} \frac{\partial c_{i,j}^s}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 D_{i,j}^p \frac{\partial c_{i,j}^p}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{(1 - \varepsilon_{p,j})}{\varepsilon_{p,j}} \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 D_{i,j}^s \frac{\partial c_{i,j}^s}{\partial r} \right), \quad (5a)$$

$$0 = f_{\text{bind}}(c_j^p, c_j^s). \quad (5b)$$

185 The boundary conditions are given on $(0, T_{\text{end}}] \times (0, L)$ by

$$\left(\varepsilon_{p,j} D_{i,j}^p \frac{\partial c_{i,j}^p}{\partial r} + (1 - \varepsilon_{p,j}) D_{i,j}^s \frac{\partial c_{i,j}^s}{\partial r} \right) \Big|_{r=R_{p,j}} = k_{f,i,j} \left(c_i^b - c_{i,j}^p \Big|_{r=R_{p,j}} \right), \quad (6a)$$

$$- \left(\varepsilon_{p,j} D_{i,j}^p \frac{\partial c_{i,j}^p}{\partial r} + (1 - \varepsilon_{p,j}) D_{i,j}^s \frac{\partial c_{i,j}^s}{\partial r} \right) \Big|_{r=R_{c,j}} = 0. \quad (6b)$$

186 Here, $D_{p,i,j}$ denotes the pore diffusion coefficients for the respective particle
 187 type j . The initial conditions at $t = 0$ are given by

$$c_{i,j}^p \Big|_{t=0} = c_{\text{init},i,j}^p \quad \text{in } (0, L) \times (R_{c,j}, R_{p,j}), \quad (7a)$$

$$c_{i,j}^s \Big|_{t=0} = c_{\text{init},i,j}^s \quad \text{in } (0, L) \times (R_{c,j}, R_{p,j}), \quad (7b)$$

188 and, when we consider a rapid-equilibrium binding, have to be consistent
 189 with the algebraic binding equation (8b).

190 *2.2. Binding Model*

191 We note that each particle type can employ a different binding model
192 and drop the particle index j in this section for better readability. The
193 transport equations are complemented by a binding model that describes the
194 transition of molecules between mobile and stationary phase. The binding
195 model function f_{bind} gives the equilibrium between mobile and stationary
196 phase concentrations:

$$\frac{\partial c^s}{\partial t} = f_{\text{bind}}(c^p, c^s). \quad (8a)$$

If adsorption kinetics happens on a much faster time scale than transport
phenomena, one can assume the binding to happen infinitely fast and thus
197 to be in rapid-equilibrium, i.e.

$$0 = f_{\text{bind}}(c^p, c^s). \quad (8b)$$

198 There exists a multitude of binding models and variations (see e.g. Guio-
199 chon et al., 2006, chapters 3 and 4), with a considerable selection available
200 in CADET. Here, we specify only the SMA binding model (Brooks and
201 Cramer, 1992) which, among others, is considered in the benchmarking.

202 The SMA is often used in ion-exchange chromatography, where the bind-
203 ing process is controlled by a mobile phase modifier (salt), which competes
204 for the binding sites. Initially, all binding sites are occupied by monovalent
205 salt ions, i.e. one ion per site. Characteristic charges $\nu_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$ are added to
206 each component i , which determine how many binding sites a correspond-
207 ing molecule occupies when adsorbed. Depending on its geometry, a bound
208 molecule might additionally block off some binding sites without binding to

209 them. The number of shielded binding sites is given by a steric shielding fac-
 210 tor $\sigma_i \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$. The finite number of total binding sites on the particle surface is
 211 determined by the particle's ionic capacity $\Lambda \in \mathbb{R}^+$, limiting the solid phase
 212 concentrations. The SMA model requires the presence of a salt component,
 213 which we choose as component $i = 0$ in the following. The balance equation
 214 for the binding sites is given by

$$\Lambda = c_0^s + \sum_{i=1}^{N_c-1} \nu_i c_i^s, \quad (9)$$

215 meaning that all binding sites are always occupied (electro-neutrality). Tak-
 216 ing shielded binding sites into account, the number of available binding sites
 217 \bar{c}_0^s is calculated by

$$\bar{c}_0^s = \Lambda - \sum_{i=1}^{N_c-1} (\nu_i + \sigma_i) c_i^s = c_0^s - \sum_{i=1}^{N_c-1} \sigma_i c_i^s. \quad (10)$$

218 The binding model function for non-salt components is given by

$$f_{\text{bind},i}(c^p, c^s) = k_{a,i}(\bar{c}_0^s)^{\nu_i} c_i^p - k_{d,i}(c_0^p)^{\nu_i} c_i^s \quad \forall i \geq 2. \quad (11a)$$

It follows by the electro-neutrality condition (9) that the salt ions take on
 219 the following ratio

$$f_{\text{bind},1}(c^p, c^s) = \Lambda - \left(c_0^s + \sum_{i=1}^{N_c-1} \nu_i c_i^s \right). \quad (11b)$$

220 3. Numerical Methods

221 3.1. Spatial Discretization

222 The spatial DG discretizations developed in this section are based on the
 223 work of Kronbichler (2021) and Winters et al. (2021) and the book by Hes-
 224 thaven and Warburton (2008). To begin with, we derive a discrete calculus
 225 toolbox for nodal spectral elements.

226 3.1.1. Nodal Element Toolbox

227 To optimize memory usage, computational cost and numerical condition,
 228 element-wise computations are carried out on a one-dimensional reference
 229 element $E := [-1, 1]$. Nodal elements are commonly constructed on either
 230 Gauß-Legendre or Legendre-Gauß-Lobatto (LGL) points due to (near) opti-
 231 mal behavior regarding polynomial interpolation and numerical quadrature.
 232 We construct a nodal interpolatory polynomial of degree N_d on the LGL
 233 points $\{\xi_k\}_{k=0}^{N_d} \subset E$ using the Lagrange basis $\mathcal{L}^{N_d} := \{\ell_j\}_{j=0}^{N_d}$ given by

$$\ell_j(\xi) = \prod_{\substack{i=0 \\ i \neq j}}^{N_d} \frac{\xi - \xi_i}{\xi_j - \xi_i} \quad \text{such that} \quad \ell_j(\xi_i) = \delta_{ij} := \begin{cases} 1, & i = j, \\ 0, & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

234 That is, the interpolatory polynomial $p \in \mathbb{P}^{N_d}(E)$ of a sought solution $c \in$
 235 $\mathcal{C}^\infty(E)$ on the spatial domain E takes the form

$$p(\xi) = \sum_{j=0}^{N_d} \ell_j(\xi) \underline{L}_j \approx c(\xi), \quad (13)$$

236 with

$$\underline{L}_j = c(\xi_j) \in \mathbb{R} \quad \forall j \in \{0, \dots, N_d\}. \quad (14)$$

237 The choice of LGL interpolation points simplifies the computation of surface
 238 integrals, since the required approximation values at element boundaries are
 239 stored as polynomial coefficients $\underline{L}_0, \underline{L}_{N_d}$. However, modal (normalized) Ja-
 240 cobi polynomials $\{\mathcal{P}_j^{(\alpha, \beta)}\}_{j=0}^{N_d}$ can be used to calculate integrals of the form

$$\int_E \mathcal{P}_i^{(\alpha, \beta)}(\xi) \mathcal{P}_j^{(\alpha, \beta)}(\xi) w^{(\alpha, \beta)}(\xi) d\xi = \delta_{i,j} \quad (15)$$

241 exactly. Here, $\alpha, \beta > -1$ are parameters of the normalized Jacobi polynomial
 242 basis functions, which are orthonormal with respect to the weight function

243 $w^{(\alpha,\beta)}(\xi) := (1+\xi)^\alpha(1-\xi)^\beta$ as expressed in Eq. (15). To exploit this property,
 244 we recover nodal (Lagrange) expansion coefficients $\underline{L} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_d+1}$ from modal
 245 (Jacobi) expansion coefficients $\underline{P}^{(\alpha,\beta)} \in \mathbb{R}^{N_d+1}$ via the relation (Hesthaven
 246 and Warburton, 2002)

$$\underline{L} = \mathcal{V}^{(\alpha,\beta)} \underline{P}^{(\alpha,\beta)}. \quad (16)$$

247 Here, \underline{L} and $\underline{P}^{(\alpha,\beta)}$ are vectors of coordinates in the respective bases and
 248 $\mathcal{V}_{i,j}^{(\alpha,\beta)} := \mathcal{P}_j^{(\alpha,\beta)}(\xi_i)$ is the (invertible) Vandermonde matrix of the correspond-
 249 ing Jacobi polynomial basis.

250 These relations are used to compute the mass matrix $\mathcal{M}^{(\alpha,\beta)} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N_d+1) \times (N_d+1)}$,
 251

$$\mathcal{M}_{i,j}^{(\alpha,\beta)} := \int_E \ell_i(\xi) \ell_j(\xi) w^{(\alpha,\beta)}(\xi) d\xi = \left(\mathcal{V}^{(\alpha,\beta)} (\mathcal{V}^{(\alpha,\beta)})^T \right)_{i,j}^{-1}, \quad (17a)$$

exactly. Alternatively, the mass matrix can be approximated using LGL
 quadrature and collocation of interpolation and quadrature points. For $\alpha =$
 252 $\beta = 0$ this yields

$$\mathcal{M}_{\text{LGL}} := \sum_{k=0}^N \ell_i(\xi_k) \ell_j(\xi_k) \tilde{w}_k = \text{diag}(\underline{\tilde{w}}) \approx \mathcal{M}^{(0,0)}, \quad (17b)$$

253 with $\underline{\tilde{w}} := [\tilde{w}_0, \dots, \tilde{w}_{N_d}]$ being the quadrature weights. We note that by
 254 computing the integral of a Lagrange polynomial of order N_d using LGL
 255 quadrature instead of exact integration, we trade integration accuracy for
 256 compute time since M_{LGL} is diagonal but LGL quadrature is only exact for
 257 polynomials of degree up to $2N_d - 1$. We refer to a DGSEM using collocation
 258 of polynomial interpolation nodes and quadrature nodes as collocation
 259 DGSEM. The system Jacobian of a collocation DGSEM is additionally more

260 sparse (c.f. figure 1) due to the diagonal mass matrix, and is thus expected to
 261 facilitate a more performant factorization due to reduction in computational
 262 operations and memory requirements associated with greater sparsity. This
 263 additional sparsity increases with the polynomial degree.

264 The differentiation matrix $\mathcal{D} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N_d+1) \times (N_d+1)}$ is given by

$$\mathcal{D}_{i,j} := \frac{\partial \ell_j}{\partial \xi}(\xi_i). \quad (18)$$

265 We also introduce the stiffness matrix $\mathcal{S}^{(\alpha,\beta)} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N_d+1) \times (N_d+1)}$, which can be
 266 calculated exactly as

$$\mathcal{S}_{ij}^{(\alpha,\beta)} := \int_E \ell_i \frac{d\ell_j}{d\xi} (1+\xi)^\alpha (1-\xi)^\beta d\xi = (\mathcal{M}^{(\alpha,\beta)} \mathcal{D})_{ij} \quad (19a)$$

267 and approximated for $\alpha = \beta = 0$ as

$$(\mathcal{S}_{LGL})_{ij} := \sum_{k=0}^{N_d} \ell_i(\xi_k) \frac{d\ell_j}{d\xi}(\xi_k) \tilde{w}_k = (\mathcal{M}_{LGL} \mathcal{D})_{ij} \approx \mathcal{S}_{i,j}^{(0,0)}. \quad (19b)$$

268 The so-called “lifting” matrix $\mathcal{B}^{(\alpha,\beta)} \in \mathbb{R}^{(N_d+1) \times (N_d+1)}$ is used to compute
 269 surface integrals and is given by

$$\mathcal{B}_{ij}^{(\alpha,\beta)} := \oint_{\partial E} \ell_i(\xi) \ell_j(\xi) w^{(\alpha,\beta)}(\xi) \mathbf{n} d\xi = \begin{cases} -w^{(\alpha,\beta)}(-1) & \text{for } i = j = 0, \\ w^{(\alpha,\beta)}(1) & \text{for } i = j = N_d, \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

270 Here, $\mathbf{n} \in \{-1, 1\}$ is the outwards pointing unit normal vector in 1D.

271 The DGSEM employs numerical fluxes $f^*|_\xi(c^-, c^+)$ at element boundary
 272 positions $\xi \in \partial E$, with c^-, c^+ being the respective inner and outer values,

273 where the outer values are either given by neighbouring elements or the
 274 boundary conditions. We write the numerical flux $\underline{f}^* \in \mathbb{R}^{N_d+1}$ as a vector

$$\underline{f}^* := [f^*|_{-1}(c^-, c^+), 0, \dots, 0, f^*|_1(c^-, c^+)]. \quad (21)$$

275 The following summation-by-parts (SBP) property is the discrete equiv-
 276 alent of an integration by parts and will be used to derive the so-called
 277 strong form of the DGSEM discretization, which is how the methods are
 278 implemented. For the two sets of previously defined discrete operators,
 279 $\{\mathcal{D}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{M}^{(0,0)}, \mathcal{S}^{(0,0)}\}$ and $\{\mathcal{D}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{M}_{LGL}, \mathcal{S}_{LGL}\}$, it holds that

$$\mathcal{D} = \mathcal{M}^{-1} \mathcal{S} \text{ and } \mathcal{S} + \mathcal{S}^T = \mathcal{B}, \quad (22)$$

280 with \mathcal{M} and \mathcal{S} being the mass and stiffness matrices of the respective ap-
 281 proach. The SBP property (22) was initially shown by Kopriva and Gassner
 282 (2010) for LGL and Gauß integration and also holds for the exact integration
 283 operators when $\alpha = \beta = 0$.

284 3.1.2. Discretization of the Interstitial Volume Mass Balance

285 We drop the component index i for readability in the following sections.
 286 The spatial domain $\Omega^z = (0, L)$ is divided into $N_e^z \in \mathbb{N}$ pairwise disjoint
 287 elements $\Omega_k^z := (z_k, z_{k+1}) \subseteq \Omega^z$ with $0 = z_1 < \dots < z_{N_e^z+1} = L$ such that

$$\overline{\Omega^z} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{N_e^z} \overline{\Omega_k^z}. \quad (23)$$

288 If possible, the element distribution within the physical domain should avoid
 289 underresolution of steep gradients. For spatially one-dimensional chromatog-
 290 raphy models, we typically get more or less steep gradient fronts moving

291 through the whole axial domain Ω^z . For a non-adaptive grid we therefore
 292 choose uniform element sizes $\Delta z > 0$ such that

$$\Delta z = z_{k+1} - z_k > 0 \quad \forall k \in \{1, \dots, N_e^z\}. \quad (24)$$

293 The affine mapping from the reference element to the physical domain is
 294 given for each element Ω_k by

$$z(\xi) = z_k + \frac{\Delta z}{2}(\xi + 1), \quad \xi \in [-1, 1], \quad (25)$$

295 with its inverse Jacobian

$$J^{-1} = \frac{d\xi}{dz} = \frac{2}{\Delta z}. \quad (26)$$

296 Starting point for DG is a weak formulation of the model equations. That
 297 is, we multiply the interstitial volume mass balance Eq. (2) with an arbitrary
 298 smooth test function $\phi \in \mathcal{C}^\infty(\Omega_k)$ and integrate over the spatial domain Ω_k ,
 299 giving us

$$\int_{\Omega_k^z} \phi \frac{\partial c^b}{\partial t} dz = \int_{\Omega_k^z} \phi \left(-u \frac{\partial c^b}{\partial z} + D_{\text{ax}} \frac{\partial^2 c^b}{\partial z^2} - \frac{1}{\beta_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \frac{3d_j}{R_{p,j}} k_{f,j} \left(c^b - c_j^p \Big|_{r=R_{p,j}} \right) \right) dz \quad (27)$$

300 for all $\phi \in \mathcal{C}^\infty(\Omega_k^z)$, $k \in \{1, \dots, N_e^z\}$ and with $\beta_c := \varepsilon_c / (1 - \varepsilon_c)$. To retain
 301 stability, we follow Bassi and Rebay (1997) and reformulate this second or-
 302 der equation as a first order system. To this end, we introduce auxiliary
 303 unknowns $g: (0, T_{\text{end}}] \times \Omega_k^z \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined by (weak form) auxiliary equations

$$\int_{\Omega_k^z} \phi g dz = \int_{\Omega_k^z} \phi D_{\text{ax}} \frac{\partial c^b}{\partial z} dz. \quad (28)$$

304 We arrive at the final weak formulation of the interstitial mass balance by
 305 substituting g into Eq. (27), mapping the Eqs. (27) and (28) to the reference

306 element E via Eq. (25), and then performing an integration by parts, yielding
 307 the following coupled system

$$\begin{aligned} \int_E \phi \frac{\partial c^b}{\partial t} d\xi &= J^{-1} \left(\int_E \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \xi} (uc^b - g) d\xi - \oint_{\partial E} \phi (uc^b - g) \mathbf{n} ds \right) \\ &\quad - \int_E \phi \left(\frac{1}{\beta_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \frac{3d_j}{R_{p,j}} k_{f,j} \left(c^b - c_j^p \Big|_{r=R_{p,j}} \right) \right) dz, \\ \int_E \phi g d\xi &= D_{ax} J^{-1} \left(\oint_{\partial E} \phi c^b \mathbf{n} ds - \int_E \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial z} c^b d\xi \right). \end{aligned}$$

308 Generally, a solution to the original equations is also a solution to the
 309 weak formulation but not necessarily the other way around. The equations
 310 are equivalent however, if the solution is sufficiently smooth.

311 Applying the DG discretization, we approximate the sought solution vari-
 312 able $c^b|_{\Omega_k^z}$ and auxiliary variable $g|_{\Omega_k^z}$ by interpolating Lagrange polynomials
 313 of degree N_p^z on the reference element E . We get for $t \in (0, T_{\text{end}}]$ and $\xi \in E$:

314

$$c^b(t, \xi) \approx \sum_{k=0}^{N_d^z} \underline{c}_k^b(t) \ell_k(\xi) =: c_h^b \quad (29a)$$

$$g(t, \xi) \approx \sum_{k=0}^{N_d^z} \underline{g}_k(t) \ell_k(\xi) =: g_h \quad (29b)$$

315 Here, $\underline{c}^b, \underline{g}$ are vectors of polynomial coefficients at time t . We construct a
 316 discrete DG formulation of the continuous weak form (29) by reducing the
 317 infinite dimensional space of test functions $\mathcal{C}^\infty(E)$ to the finite dimensional
 318 polynomial space $\mathbb{P}^{N_p^z}(E)$. This gives us for all $\ell \in \mathcal{L}^{N_d^z}$ the following equa-

319 tions:

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_E \ell \frac{\partial c_h^b}{\partial t} d\xi &= J^{-1} \left(\int_E \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial \xi} (uc_h^b - g_h) d\xi - \oint_{\partial E} \ell (uc_h^b - g_h) \mathbf{n} ds \right) \\
&\quad - \int_E \ell \left(\frac{1}{\beta_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \frac{3d_j}{R_{p,j}} k_{f,j} \left(c_h^b - (c_h^{p,j}) \Big|_{r=R_{p,j}} \right) \right) dz, \quad (30) \\
\int_E \ell g_h d\xi &= D_{\text{ax}} J^{-1} \left(\oint_{\partial E} \ell c_h^b \mathbf{n} ds - \int_E \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial z} c_h^b d\xi \right).
\end{aligned}$$

320 By construction, we have two values at element interfaces, allowing for
321 discontinuities. The element interfaces can be interpreted to define local
322 Riemann problems (Riemann, 1876), which can be approximately solved by
323 means of a numerical flux function (see e.g. Ketcheson et al., 2020). Thus, we
324 define the unique approximation at an interface by a numerical flux function,
325 depending on the inner and outer approximations:

$$\oint_{\partial E} \ell_j (uc_h^b - g_h) \mathbf{n} ds \approx \oint_{\partial E} \ell_j h^* (u(c_h^b)^+, u(c_h^b)^-, g_h^+, g_h^-) \mathbf{n} ds, \quad (31)$$

$$\oint_{\partial E} \ell_j c_h^b \mathbf{n} ds \approx \oint_{\partial E} \ell_j g^* ((c_h^b)^+, (c_h^b)^-) \mathbf{n} ds. \quad (32)$$

326 Here, h^* and g^* denote feasible numerical fluxes and the inner and outer
327 values at the interfaces are denoted with superscript $+$ and $-$ respectively.
328 Using the fluxes, the element-wise equations (30) are weakly coupled to neigh-
329 bouring elements or boundary conditions respectively. We come back to the
330 exact choice of the numerical flux function later.

331 We can now translate the equations into discrete operators. Overall, we

332 arrive at the element-wise ordinary differential equation (ODE) system

$$\underline{\dot{c}}^b = \frac{2}{\Delta z} \mathcal{M}^{-1} (\mathcal{D}^T \mathcal{M} (u \underline{c}^b - \underline{g}) - \mathcal{B} \underline{h}^*) - \frac{1}{\beta_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \frac{3d_j}{R_{p,j}} k_{f,j} \left(\underline{c}^b - \underline{c}^{p,j} \Big|_{R_p} \right), \quad (33a)$$

$$\underline{g} = \frac{2}{\Delta z} D_{\text{ax}} \mathcal{M}^{-1} (\mathcal{D}^T \mathcal{M} \underline{c}^b - \mathcal{B} \underline{c}^*), \quad (33b)$$

333 with $\underline{\dot{c}}^b$ denoting the vector of polynomial coefficients of the temporal deriva-
 334 tive $\partial c_h^b / \partial t$ and $\underline{c}^{p,j} \Big|_{R_p}$ the vector of polynomial coefficients at the particle
 335 surface. Depending on the chosen approach, $\mathcal{M} \in \{\mathcal{M}^{(0,0)}, \mathcal{M}_{\text{LGL}}\}$ repre-
 336 sents the mass matrix using either exact or inexact integration. We rewrite
 337 system (33) in so-called strong form by applying the SBP property (22) and
 338 using the symmetry of the mass matrix to get

$$\underline{\dot{c}}^b = \frac{2}{\Delta z} (-\mathcal{D} (u \underline{c}^b - \underline{g}) + \mathcal{M}^{-1} \mathcal{B} ((u \underline{c}^b - \underline{g}) - \underline{h}^*)) - \frac{1}{\beta_c} \sum_{j=1}^{N_p} \frac{3d_j}{R_{p,j}} k_{f,j} \left(\underline{c}^b - \underline{c}^{p,j} \Big|_{R_p} \right), \quad (34a)$$

$$\underline{g} = \frac{2}{\Delta z} D_{\text{ax}} (\mathcal{D} \underline{c}^b - \mathcal{M}^{-1} \mathcal{B} (\underline{c}^b - \underline{c}^*)), \quad (34b)$$

339 which further reduces arithmetic operations. The global approximations are
 340 discontinuous, piecewise polynomial approximations on the broken finite el-
 341 ement space

$$\mathcal{U}_h := \{u_h \in \mathcal{L}_2(\Omega^z) : u_h \Big|_{\Omega_k^z} \in \mathbb{P}^{N_e^z}(\xi_k(E)) \forall \Omega_k^z\}, \quad (35)$$

342 with ξ_k being the inverse of the mapping (25) and \mathcal{L}_2 being the space of
 343 square integrable functions.

344 *3.1.3. Numerical Fluxes*

345 The numerical flux for the advective part of the equation can be chosen
 346 as the Lax-Friedrichs flux (Cockburn et al., 2000), which for linear advection
 347 reduces to the upwind flux. For dispersive fluxes, it is reasonable (Bassi and
 348 Rebay, 1997) to choose a central numerical flux. Accordingly, we construct
 349 the numerical flux h^* as the sum of a convective and dispersive part

$$h^* (u(c_h^b)^-, u(c_h^b)^+, g_h^-, g_h^+) := u(c_h^b)^- - \frac{g_h^+ + g_h^-}{2}, \quad (36a)$$

where the superscripts $-$ and $+$ denote the inner and outer value respectively.
 The auxiliary equations are complemented by a central numerical flux (Bassi
 350 and Rebay, 1997)

$$c^* ((c_h^b)^-, (c_h^b)^+) := \frac{(c_h^b)^+ + (c_h^b)^-}{2}. \quad (36b)$$

351 *3.1.4. Boundary Conditions*

352 Danckwerts boundary conditions (3) are imposed weakly, i.e. through the
 353 numerical fluxes

$$h^*|_{z=0} := u c_{\text{in}}^b, \quad h^*|_{z=L} := u(c_h^b)^-. \quad (37a)$$

The model does not prescribe boundary conditions for the auxiliary equa-
 tions. We hence define the numerical flux for inflow and outflow boundaries
 354 as (Bassi and Rebay, 1997)

$$c^*|_{z=0} := c^b|_{z=0}, \quad c^*|_{z=L} := c^b|_{z=L}. \quad (37b)$$

355 *3.1.5. Discretization of the Particle Mass Balances*

356 We drop the particle type index j since the discretization is the same
 357 for each particle. In the following, we consider the discretization of a single

358 particle at an axial location $z_p \in \Omega^z$, i.e. $c^p(z, r, t)|_{z_p} = c^p(r, t)$. Such a
 359 discretization is associated to each LGL node ξ of each axial element Ω_k^z .

360 We begin the DG discretization by dividing the spatial domain $\Omega^r =$
 361 (R_c, R_p) by $N_e^r \in \mathbb{N}$ pairwise disjoint elements $\Omega_k^r := (r_k, r_{k+1}) \subseteq \Omega^r$, with
 362 $R_c = r_1 < \dots < r_{N_e^r+1} = R_p$ such that

$$\overline{\Omega^r} = \bigcup_{k=1}^{N_e^r} \overline{\Omega_k^r}. \quad (38)$$

363 We allow arbitrary element sizes

$$\Delta r_k := r_{k+1} - r_k > 0 \quad \forall k \in \{1, \dots, N_e^r\}, \quad (39)$$

364 since concentration profiles may behave differently depending on the specific
 365 problem and binding behavior which can be addressed by corresponding res-
 366 olutions inside the particles. The affine mapping from the reference element
 367 to the physical domain is given for each element Ω_k by

$$r_k(\xi) = r_k + \frac{\Delta r_k}{2}(\xi + 1), \quad \xi \in [-1, 1], \quad (40)$$

368 with its inverse Jacobian

$$J_k^{-1} = \frac{d\xi}{dr} = \frac{2}{\Delta r_k} \quad \forall k \in \{1, \dots, N_e^r\}. \quad (41)$$

369 Following Bassi and Rebay (1997) again, we introduce the substitutes

$$g^p(t, \xi) := D_p \frac{\partial c^p(t, \xi)}{\partial \xi}, \quad g^s(t, \xi) := \frac{1}{\beta_p} D_s \frac{\partial c^s(t, \xi)}{\partial \xi}, \quad (42)$$

370 and the corresponding auxiliary equations, which are DG-discretized to give
 371 element-wise algebraic equations to determine the polynomial coefficients of

372 the substitutes (cf. Eq. (33b)):

$$\underline{g}^p = D_p (\mathcal{D}\underline{c}^p - \mathcal{M}^{-1}\mathcal{B}(c^p - \underline{c}^{p,*})), \quad (43a)$$

$$\underline{g}^s = \frac{1}{\beta_p} D_s (\mathcal{D}\underline{c}^s - \mathcal{M}^{-1}\mathcal{B}(c^s - \underline{c}^{s,*})). \quad (43b)$$

373 The numerical fluxes are again vector notated central fluxes. We define the
 374 substitute $\underline{g} := \underline{g}^p + \underline{g}^s$ for our further considerations, with $g_h \in \mathbb{P}^{N_d^r}$ being
 375 the corresponding interpolatory polynomial.

376 The discrete weak form of the particle mass balance is now obtained
 377 following the same steps as for Eq. (30). That is we approximate the sought
 378 solution variables by interpolating polynomials

$$c^p(t, \xi) \approx \sum_{k=0}^{N_d^r} \underline{c}_k^s(t) \ell_k(\xi) =: c_h^p \quad (44a)$$

$$c^s(t, \xi) \approx \sum_{k=0}^{N_d^r} \underline{c}_k^s(t) \ell_k(\xi) =: c_h^s \quad (44b)$$

379 We then reduce the test space to $\mathbb{P}^{N_d^r}([-1, 1])$, and perform an integration
 380 by parts, which gives us for all Lagrange basis functions $\ell \in \mathcal{L}^{N_d^r}$:

$$\int_E \left(\frac{\partial c_h^p}{\partial t} + \beta_p \frac{\partial c_h^s}{\partial t} \right) \ell r_k^2(\xi) d\xi = \left(\frac{2}{\Delta r_k} \right)^2 \left(- \int_E g_h \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial \xi} r_k^2(\xi) d\xi + \oint_{\partial E} g_h \ell r_k^2(\xi) \mathbf{n} ds \right). \quad (45)$$

381 We note that, in contrast to the previous discretizations, we now have to
 382 consider the spatially dependent metric term

$$r_k^2(\xi) = r_k^2 + 2 \frac{\Delta r_k}{2} r_k (1 + \xi) + \left(\frac{\Delta r_k}{2} \right)^2 (1 + \xi)^2, \quad (46)$$

383 inside the integral. Applying LGL quadrature, the metric term is evaluated
 384 on the inner particle boundary, i.e. $r = 0$, which results in an algebraic equa-
 385 tion. It showed that this additional algebraic equation causes severe stiffness

386 such that we decided to neglect the collocation DGSEM here. However,
 387 each summand of Eq. (46) yields an integral that can be calculated exactly
 388 via the respective normalized Jacobi polynomial basis, i.e. with $\alpha = 0$ and
 389 $\beta \in \{0, 1, 2\}$ respectively. Defining the following discrete operators

$$\mathcal{M}_k^r := \mathcal{M}^{0,0} r_k^2 + \mathcal{M}^{0,1} r_k \Delta r_k + \mathcal{M}^{0,2} \left(\frac{\Delta r_k}{2} \right)^2, \quad (47a)$$

$$\mathcal{B}_k^r := \mathcal{B}^{0,0} r_k^2 + \mathcal{B}^{0,1} r_k \Delta r_k + \mathcal{B}^{0,2} \left(\frac{\Delta r_k}{2} \right)^2, \quad (47b)$$

390 we get the element wise particle discretization as

$$\underline{\dot{c}}^p + \beta_p \underline{\dot{c}}^s = \left(\frac{2}{\Delta r_k} \right)^2 \left[- \left((\mathcal{M}_k^r)^{-1} \mathcal{D}^T \mathcal{M}_k^r \right) \underline{g} + (\mathcal{M}^r)^{-1} \mathcal{B}_k^r \underline{g}^* \right]. \quad (48)$$

391 Here, $\underline{\dot{c}}^s$ denotes the vector of polynomial coefficients of the temporal deriva-
 392 tive $\partial c_h^s / \partial t$ and the numerical flux is again a vector notated central flux. We
 393 note that the particle discretization (48) can not be rewritten in strong form
 394 since the SBP property (22) does not hold for the operators defined in (47).

395 The weak formulation of the complementing binding Eq. (8b) is given for
 396 every element Ω_k^r by

$$0 = \int_E \sum_{k=0}^{N_d^r} f_{\text{bind}}(c^b(\xi_k), c^s(\xi_k)) \ell_k(\xi) \ell(\xi) r_k^2(\xi) \frac{\Delta r_k}{2} d\xi \quad \forall \ell \in \mathcal{L}^{N_d^r}. \quad (49)$$

Here, we have approximated the binding model via (Lagrange) polynomial
 interpolation and mapped the equation to the reference element E . Applying
 397 the inverse mass matrix yields

$$\underline{0} = f_{\text{bind}}(\underline{c}^b, \underline{c}^s). \quad (50)$$

398 We note that the polynomial approximation of the nonlinear binding func-
 399 tion might lead to aliasing errors which can be reduced by grid refinement.

400 Overall, we get with Eqs. (34a), (48) and (50) a DAE system of size

$$s := N_e^z (N_d^z + 1) N_c (1 + 2N_e^r (N_d^r + 1)). \quad (51)$$

401 3.1.6. Boundary Conditions

402 We reformulate the film diffusion boundary condition Eq. (6a) for the
403 outer boundary element $\Omega_{N_e^r}^r$ of each particle type as

$$\left(D^p \frac{\partial c^p}{\partial \xi} + \frac{1}{\beta_p} D^s \frac{\partial c^s}{\partial \xi} \right) \Big|_{\xi=1} = \frac{\Delta r_{N_e^r}}{2} \frac{1}{\varepsilon_p} k_f \left[c^p - c^b \Big|_{\xi=1} \right] \quad \text{on } (0, T_{\text{end}}] \times (0, L), \quad (52)$$

404 and accordingly define the outer boundary numerical flux as

$$g^*(g^p, g^s) \Big|_{r=R_p} := \frac{\Delta r_{N_e^r}}{2} \frac{1}{\varepsilon_p} k_f (c_N^p - c^b) \quad \text{on } (0, T_{\text{end}}] \times (0, L).$$

405 At the inner particle boundary, we reformulate boundary condition Eq. (6b)

406 for the inner boundary element Ω_1^r of each particle as

$$\left(D^p \frac{\partial c^p}{\partial \xi} + \frac{1}{\beta_p} D^s \frac{\partial c^s}{\partial \xi} \right) \Big|_{\xi=-1} = 0 \quad \text{on } (0, T_{\text{end}}] \times (0, L), \quad (53)$$

407 and accordingly define the inner boundary numerical flux as

$$g^*(g^p, g^s) \Big|_{r=0} := 0 \quad \text{on } (0, T_{\text{end}}] \times (0, L). \quad (54)$$

408 Since there are no boundary conditions given for the auxiliary equations
409 Eqs. (43a) and (43b), we employ solid wall boundary conditions (Bassi and
410 Rebay, 1997)

$$c^* \left((c^p)^-, (c^p)^+ \right) := (c^p)^-, \quad c^* \left((c^s)^-, (c^s)^+ \right) := (c^s)^- \quad \text{on } (0, T_{\text{end}}] \times (0, L), \quad (55)$$

411 at the inner and outer particle boundaries.

412 *3.2. Temporal Discretization*

413 The spatial semi-discretization of the model equations leads to a coupled
 414 DAE system to be integrated in time. The initial value problem (IVP) to be
 415 solved is given by the residual formulation

$$R\left(t, y, \frac{\partial y}{\partial t}\right) = 0, \quad y(t_0) = y_0, \quad \frac{\partial y}{\partial t}(t_0) = \dot{y}_0, \quad (56)$$

416 with initial values $y_0, \dot{y}_0 \in \mathbb{R}^s$, time variable $t \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$, initial time $t_0 \in \mathbb{R}_0^+$,
 417 global state and state derivative vectors $y, \dot{y} \in \mathbb{R}^s$ and R being the residual
 418 function of the spatially discretized model equations.

419 There are various time integration methods that can solve DAE systems.
 420 However, depending on the specific problem, the choice of a suitable time
 421 integration method is crucial to provide an overall efficient scheme. Since
 422 chromatographic problems are often stiff (see e.g. Gu, 2015, chapter 3.7), any
 423 general purpose solver should employ an implicit time integration method
 424 to allow larger time steps (and thus efficiency) while maintaining stability
 425 (Lambert, 1991, section 7). To discretize the DAE in time, we choose a vari-
 426 able order BDF with adaptive step size and order developed by Hindmarsh
 427 et al. (2005), which is also used for the FV implementation. The method is
 428 publicly available as implicit differential-algebraic solver (IDAS) within the
 429 suite of nonlinear and differential/algebraic equation solvers (SUNDIALS).
 430 The method order ranges from 1 to 5, with the BDF of order q given by the
 431 multistep formula

$$\sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_{n,i} y_{n-i} = h_n \dot{y}_n, \quad (57)$$

432 with y_n and \dot{y}_n being the computed approximations to the global state and
 433 state derivative, respectively, and $h_n = t_n - t_{n-1}$ being the time step size.

434 The application of BDF method Eq. (57) to the DAE system Eq. (56) yields
 435 a nonlinear algebraic system to be solved at each step:

$$G(y_n) := R \left(t_n, y_n, \frac{1}{h_n} \sum_{i=0}^q \alpha_{n,i} y_{n-i} \right) = 0. \quad (58)$$

436 To solve this system, IDAS uses a Newton iteration which repetitively
 437 requires the solution of a linear system given by

$$J [y_n(m+1) - y_n(m)] = -G(y_n(m)), \quad (59)$$

438 with $y_n(m)$ being the m th approximation to y_n . J is some approximation to
 439 the system Jacobian

$$J = \frac{\partial G}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial R}{\partial y} + \alpha \frac{\partial R}{\partial \dot{y}}, \quad (60)$$

440 with $\alpha = \alpha_{n,0}/h_n$. The scalar α changes whenever the step size or method
 441 order changes.

442 We use the publicly available Eigen library (Guennebaud and Benoît,
 443 2010) to perform dense and sparse matrix-vector operations. The built-
 444 in sparse LU factorization is used to solve the linear system Eq. (59). A
 445 built-in reordering of the Jacobian reduces (fill-in) non-zero entries during
 446 factorization and only needs to be computed once, since the sparsity pattern
 447 is static. Sparse matrices are stored in compressed row major form.

448 3.2.1. *Jacobian*

449 To employ the IDAS BDF method, we need to estimate the system Jaco-
 450 bian J according to Eq. (60). The second part of the Jacobian, i.e. $\partial R/\partial \dot{y}$,
 451 is very sparse and easily derived manually. The first part of the Jacobian
 452 could be determined analytically or approximated by finite differences of the

453 form:

$$R(t, y + e) - R(t, y) \approx \frac{\partial R}{\partial y} e, \quad (61)$$

454 with $e \in \mathbb{R}^s$ being some scaled unit vector. To spare the computational effort
455 of the FD calculation, we derived the Jacobian analytically.

456 The linear DGSEM discretization of the mass balance equations ensures
457 static entries in the Jacobian, which are depicted in figure 1. These static
458 entries only need to be calculated when parameters (e.g. velocity, disper-
459 sion) change. Conversely, entries due to nonlinear binding models must be
460 calculated in every Newton iteration.

461 **4. Software Verification**

462 To verify our implementation, we perform order-of-accuracy tests, which
463 are considered the most resilient and rigorous testing procedure. Here, we
464 test whether the discrete approximation converges to the exact solution with
465 an experimental rate that asymptotically approaches the theoretical rate
466 (Knupp and Kambiz, 2002) given by $N_d + 1$ for a DG scheme. The ex-
467 perimental order of convergence (*EOC*) is computed by

$$EOC = \frac{\log\left(\frac{\varepsilon_k}{\varepsilon_{k-1}}\right)}{\log\left(\frac{n_{k-1}}{n_k}\right)}, \quad (62)$$

468 with $n_k \in \mathbb{N}$ being the number of degrees of freedom (DoF) of the k th spa-
469 tial resolution and $\varepsilon_k \in \mathbb{R}^+$ being some error norm of the corresponding
470 discretization error. To this end, we use arbitrary precision reference chro-
471 matograms with provable error bounds, which are available for linear models
472 and can be computed using the open-source software CADET-semi-analytic

473 (Leweke and von Lieres, 2016). The relative and absolute time integration
474 tolerances of IDAS are selected as 10^{-10} and 10^{-12} , respectively, to ensure
475 that the spatial error dominates for the considered error ranges.

476 We verify our implementation for each transport model with one-component
477 and linear kinetic and rapid-equilibrium binding settings. This gives us a to-
478 tal of 8 test cases, the respective model parameters are specified in table S2.

479 The results for both the collocation DGSEM and exact integration DGSEM
480 (note that the particles for the GRM are always discretized by an exact
481 integration DGSEM) are given in the supplementary material (and in Ta-
482 ble 1 for the GRM with surface diffusion) and verify all our implementations.
483 While the DG methods with $N_d = 1$ show the expected asymptotic behav-
484 ior, i.e. they approach the expected theoretical rate of 2, higher polynomial
485 degrees exhibit even higher convergence rates until the error tolerances are
486 approached. To further investigate the asymptotic behavior, an extensive
487 analysis using arbitrary precision arithmetic would be necessary. Since each
488 discretization converges to the exact solution and the convergence rates pos-
489 itively correlate with the polynomial degree, while $N_d = 1$ already shows the
490 expected asymptotic behavior, we limit the scope of this work on this end.

491 **5. Benchmarking**

492 To enhance the reproducibility of our results, we have made the evaluation
493 scripts publicly available (Breuer et al., 2023).

494 Since DG technically yields a variety of schemes, one for each polynomial
495 degree, we consider multiple polynomial degrees within each benchmark. As
496 the IDAS BDF method is accurate up to order 5, special interest lies on

497 the polynomial degrees ≤ 4 . Depending on the time integration tolerances,
498 (slightly) larger polynomial degrees are also relevant.

499 To make statements with broad applicability, we cover a wide range of
500 simulations with our benchmarks and accordingly consider various settings.
501 That is, we take up again the one-component linear settings, c.f. Table S2,
502 and recreate a four-component SMA case originally considered by Püttmann
503 et al. (2013) and also replicated and benchmarked by Meyer et al. (2020), c.f.
504 parameter Table S3. Finally, we consider a two-component Langmuir setting
505 defined in Table S1, which is meant to specifically challenge the oscillatory
506 DG methods. High resolution simulations serve as reference solutions for
507 the column outlet profiles of nonlinear models. If not stated otherwise, dis-
508 cretizations are gradually refined by increasing (doubling) the number of DG
509 elements and FV cells respectively (h-refinement). Since we investigate the
510 spatial discretization accuracy, time integration error tolerances are chosen
511 such that the spatial discretization errors dominate. We are also specifically
512 interested in the performance within engineering accuracy, which we define as
513 a maximal deviation of at most 1% from the reference at the column outlet.

514 *5.1. Collocation DGSEM vs. Exact Integration DGSEM*

515 The objective of the following considerations is to find whether the exact
516 integration DGSEM or the collocation DGSEM is generally or systematically,
517 i.e. depending on the discretization or model parameters, superior regarding
518 computational efficiency. To place our analysis on a broad basis, we consider
519 a total of 13 settings given in parameter Tables S1, S2, S3: The 8 linear
520 settings from above, one nonlinear SMA setting for each transport model,
521 and two nonlinear Langmuir settings for the LRM. The results are partly

522 given in this document (see Figure 2), the entire study for every setting can
523 be found in the supplementary material.

524 The benchmarks confirm that the exact integration DGSEM mostly yields
525 more accurate approximations per DoF, which does not necessarily translate
526 into a performance advantage since the evaluation of the collocation scheme
527 is computationally less demanding. Regarding computational performance,
528 neither scheme is universally superior. The exact integration DGSEM only
529 shows to be consistently more efficient for polynomial degree 1. For the
530 more relevant polynomial degrees $N_d \geq 3$, however, we observe a systematic
531 advantage of the collocation DGSEM. The difference in required arithmetic
532 operations to evaluate the two schemes increases with higher polynomial de-
533 gree due to the sparsity of the mass-matrix, c.f. figure 1. Accordingly, the
534 collocation DGSEM improves in terms of performance with higher polyno-
535 mial degrees, which is observed in every considered setting. An example
536 benchmark is shown in Figure 2 for a LRM with rapid-equilibrium linear
537 binding, which depicts this behavior as it mostly occurs. In this particular
538 benchmark, we observe a performance advantage of the collocation DGSEM
539 for polynomial degree $N_d \in \{4, 5, 6\}$ and parity for $N_d = 3$. Yet, it seems to
540 be highly problem-dependent to find a polynomial degree for which the collo-
541 cation DGSEM is generally superior. For the settings considered in this work,
542 the collocation DGSEM is mostly advantageous for $N_d \geq 4$ while at par for
543 $N_d = 3$. Since we considered a broad range of simulations, we expect similar
544 behavior for many other settings. Thus, if not stated otherwise, we consider
545 the collocation DGSEM for the bulk discretizations in the subsequent parts
546 of this work.

547 *5.2. DG vs. FV*

548 The WENO FV scheme, which serves as a benchmark here, is globally sec-
549 ond order accurate. However, the algorithm and code are highly optimized,
550 e.g., by exploiting a specific Jacobian structure and by using a custom matrix
551 factorization. Additionally, the FV implementation supports parallelization.

552 Due to its arbitrary order (i.e. > 2), DG generally requires a smaller dis-
553 crete problem size to achieve a specific approximation accuracy for sufficiently
554 smooth solutions compared to FV, which reduces the overall computational
555 demands. Therefore, we analyze both the discrete problem size and the per-
556 formance of the two methods and consider all three transport models with
557 linear and SMA binding models.

558 For every considered model and setting, we observe that the performance
559 advantage of higher order (> 2) DG especially pays of for larger discrete
560 problem sizes, i.e. for more complex settings or tighter error tolerances. Con-
561 versely, the performance advantage can be less significant for the most simple
562 settings and engineering error tolerances, e.g. for linear one-component set-
563 tings as defined in Table S2. This typically occurs with high order methods
564 on small problem sizes. However, even slight performance advantages can
565 make a difference considering that they scale with the number of compo-
566 nents, number of units of the chromatographic system and with the number
567 of simulations.

568 For medium complexity models such as the four-component LRMP SMA
569 setting defined in Table S3, a considerable performance advantage of an order
570 of magnitude is already observed for a single simulation and with respect to
571 engineering tolerances (cf. Figure 3). Although both the LRM and LRMP

572 are spatially discretized only for the bulk mass balance, the performance
573 advantage of the DG scheme is greater for the LRMP than for the LRM, since
574 we additionally drop the corresponding particle equation (film diffusion) for
575 each axial DoF spared.

576 The most complex setting considered here is a four-component GRM
577 with SMA binding. To establish a fair comparison, we apply near optimal
578 grid refinement strategies. That is, we determine an optimal FV refinement
579 strategy among $N_e^z = 2^k$, $N_e^r \in \{2^k, 2^{k-1}, 2^{k-2}\}$ with $k \in \{5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$ and
580 apply near optimal DG discretizations by selecting particle discretizations
581 that fit the respective bulk discretization accuracy. The results are given in
582 Figure 4 and show great superiority of the DG method, even in comparison to
583 parallelized FV simulations. Since the required number of DoF is comparably
584 high for this setting, we see a considerable computational advantage already
585 for low accuracy approximations. For any error tolerance, the DG method
586 with $N_d^z \in \{3, 4, 5\}$ shows a computational advantage of at least an order
587 of magnitude compared to the FV simulations, and remains superior when
588 compared to the multi-thread FV simulations (note that the use of 6 threads
589 gave optimal FV performance). For high accuracy approximations (i.e., \mathcal{L}^∞
590 error $\approx 3 \cdot 10^{-4}$), DG with $N_d^z = 5$ is 71.73 times faster than the single thread
591 FV simulation.

592 Overall, our benchmarks show substantial computational advantages of
593 the DG method for every transport model. Moreover, the DG method for
594 polynomial degrees ≥ 2 consistently performed better than the FV method
595 for the settings considered here, even for small discrete problem sizes and we
596 thus expect similar behavior for a wide range of simulations.

597 A remaining question is that of optimal polynomial degree and refinement
598 strategy. Since this is very problem dependent, we can only give general rec-
599 ommendations and instructions on how to adapt in specific situations. In-
600 creasing the polynomial degree (p-refinement) can be an attractive strategy
601 for spatial refinement as this also increases the theoretical order of conver-
602 gence. On the other hand, fewer elements mean less stabilization and might
603 cause numerical artifacts, i.e. larger approximation errors. By adding more
604 elements (h-refinement), we increase stability at the cost of a worse DoF to
605 error reduction ratio. Moreover, depending on the choice of time integration
606 tolerances, high order spatial convergence can be dominated by lower order
607 time integration, whereas forcing excessively small time steps also causes
608 computational inefficiency. It is thus our general recommendation to choose
609 a mixed h- and p-refinement strategy for the axial polynomial degree, that
610 is $3 \leq N_d^z \leq 5$ but always $N_d^z \geq 2$ and hardly ever $N_d^z \gg 5$. Regarding
611 the particle discretization, we usually do not depend on stabilization since
612 there is no advection, and we thus mostly recommend a p-refinement. There
613 might be settings however, where (non-equidistant) multiple elements might
614 be beneficial, i.e. in the case that solute molecules do not penetrate the
615 whole particle or if we have steep concentration fronts due to competitive
616 binding and displacement. The option of choosing individual polynomial de-
617 grees for axial and particle discretization was exploited in the GRM SMA
618 benchmark 4 and shows to be advantageous compared to an h-refinement
619 benchmark, see Figure 5.

620 *5.3. Oscillations*

621 As a linear high order method, the DG schemes we derived are non-
622 monotonous and might thus cause persistent oscillations and profoundly un-
623 physical negative values around discontinuities and steep gradients. The
624 dispersive terms in every chromatographic transport model prevent discon-
625 tinuities but steep gradients might still appear and can only be resolved by
626 increasing the discrete problem size, i.e. polynomial degree and number of
627 elements. Since this also inflates computation times, we investigate in the
628 following how steep gradients affect the DG performance compared to the
629 nonlinear WENO FV method.

630 Steep and self-sharpening concentration fronts are typically associated
631 with convex-upward binding models, such as the Langmuir model (Guiochon
632 et al., 2006, p. 101). Replicating an example from Shipilova et al. (2008),
633 we consider two settings for a two-component LRM with rapid-equilibrium
634 Langmuir binding, the respective parameters are given in Table S1. The
635 first setting employs a rather modest dispersion coefficient (as in Shipilova
636 et al. (2008)) while the other setting exhibits very low dispersion and is
637 expected to yield more steep gradients and thus to be more challenging. The
638 first component has a greater affinity for the binding sites such that the
639 second component is eluted first and builds up a steep concentration front,
640 see Figure 6. Meyer et al. (2018) showed that the more disperse setting can
641 indeed be accurately approximated by DG, but the authors did not provide
642 a benchmark for a non-oscillatory scheme.

643 Figure 6, for instance, depicts the behavior of the WENO FV and DG
644 with third order polynomials for the less dispersive setting. Here, DG devel-

645 ops oscillations at the steep concentration fronts when coarser discretizations
 646 are applied (see $N_e = 32$ in Figure 6). Under grid refinement, oscillations
 647 appear less frequently but the peak does not reduce substantially between
 648 $N_e = 32$ and $N_e = 128$ and undershoots strike the negative region, which is
 649 physically not allowed. In contrast to this behavior, the WENO FV scheme
 650 “essentially” shows no oscillations, and additional artificial dispersion domi-
 651 nates the approximation error (see lower row in Figure 6).

652 Figure 7 shows the benchmark and Figure 8 depicts the behavior of the
 653 largest negative value for the more and less dispersive settings, the exact
 654 numbers can be found in the supplementary materials. We first consider the
 655 less dispersive setting and see how negative concentration values are hardly
 656 an issue for the FV scheme, while they appear with substantial amplitude for
 657 the DG scheme for lower resolutions. Apparently, the DG scheme shows some
 658 breakthrough behavior, where it overcomes the oscillations and, thus, the
 659 negative concentration issue (cf. Figure 8), and starts to converge with the
 660 theoretical order. This happens between $N_e^z = 256$ and 512 for polynomial
 661 degree 3, where the largest negative concentration value rapidly shrinks from
 662 $> \cdot 10^{-1}$ to $< \cdot 10^{-8}$ and the convergence order rises from 1.75 and 2.8 up
 663 to 3.91 and 4.13 for the L^∞ and L^1 error respectively. The DG schemes
 664 with polynomial degrees 4 and 5 show similar behavior, but already between
 665 $N_e^z = 128$ and $N_e = 256$. We conclude that for this setting all schemes are
 666 rather inaccurate for lower resolutions, due to oscillations for DG and due to
 667 severe artificial dispersion for FV. While the DG scheme requires very high
 668 resolutions to overcome the oscillation issue, the FV scheme steadily reduces
 669 artificial dispersion and thus begins to dominate computationally for medium

670 resolutions. For higher resolutions the oscillations vanish and the DG schemes
671 become more efficient and catch up computationally. This however happens
672 after the more relevant range of engineering accuracy. Only for tighter error
673 tolerances $< 10^{-3}$, we observe an increasing performance advantage of the
674 DG schemes.

675 For the more dispersive setting, the approximations satisfy engineering
676 standards rather quickly, compared to the less dispersive setting. Interest-
677 ingly, the FV scheme shows a considerable computational advantage for very
678 low resolutions. The artificially dispersive behavior of the FV scheme suits
679 the larger physical dispersion of this setting, while oscillations still cause sub-
680 stantial approximation errors for DG. For moderate and higher resolutions
681 however, the DG schemes quickly become more efficient and outperform the
682 FV method again (cf. Figure 7). While lower DG resolutions again suffer
683 from considerable oscillations and thus negative concentration values, they
684 vanish rather quickly with spatial refinement, compared to the less disper-
685 sive setting (cf. Figure 8). Thus, the DG scheme quickly becomes more
686 efficient leading to a decisively earlier overtake during the relevant range of
687 engineering precision, e.g. at an error of about $3 \cdot 10^{-2}$ for DG with $N_d = 5$.

688 In summary, there are indeed chromatographic settings for which con-
689 siderable oscillations occur with linear DG, and for which the WENO FV
690 method can be beneficial for the relevant range of engineering accuracy. How-
691 ever, we only expect this behavior for particularly challenging settings that
692 combine self-sharpening fronts with extremely low dispersion coefficients.
693 One could artificially increase the dispersion parameters to avoid oscillations
694 but we consider this approach unscientific, especially for parameter estima-

695 tion, since we do not solve for the original model anymore. An essentially
696 non-oscillatory DG scheme could be beneficial for those settings but would
697 also decrease performance elsewhere.

698 **6. Conclusion**

699 We developed spatial DG discretizations for three chromatography mod-
700 els, including the General Rate Model with surface diffusion and particle size
701 distribution. Hereby we have extended existing work by a DG variation, the
702 collocation DGSEM, which showed to be advantageous, and a DGSEM for
703 the GRM particle discretization to allow non-equidistant particle resolutions
704 and solid core shell particles. We implemented the methods as an extension
705 to the open source chromatography simulator CADET, making their use and
706 implementation publicly available for the first time.

707 Compared to lower order FV, we confirm the computational superiority of
708 DG in chromatography for general use cases and found that the performance
709 advantage increases with model complexity, where larger discrete problem
710 sizes occur. Investigating potential drawbacks of oscillatory high order DG in
711 chromatography, we found that the second order WENO FV method can be
712 advantageous for particularly challenging settings with steep self sharpening
713 concentration fronts and low dispersion. While DG is generally able to resolve
714 steep concentration fronts, oscillations can lead to performance loss within
715 lower (engineering) error ranges. Hence it is beneficial to also have a non-
716 oscillatory scheme available.

717 Throughout this work, we confirmed that the FV CADET and DG CADET
718 implementations solve the same underlying models. Moreover, the two codes

719 are used to mutually validate each other, which is especially important for
720 nonlinear models where no analytical solutions exist.

721 The results of this work particularly encourage future research: An (es-
722 sentially) non-oscillatory DG scheme will be developed to improve perfor-
723 mance for problems with steep concentration fronts. Moreover, an arbitrary
724 order spatial DG discretization for spatially two dimensional chromatogra-
725 phy models (see e.g. Qamar et al., 2017; Parveen et al., 2015; David et al.,
726 2018) will be developed. Here the radial cylindrical coordinate is added to
727 the spatial domain of the interstitial volume mass balance to resolve radial
728 gradients within the column. Since this significantly increases the discrete
729 problem size, we expect great performance of high order DG methods.

730 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

731 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial inter-
732 ests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work
733 reported in this paper.

734 **CRedit authorship contribution statement**

735 Jan Breuer: Methodology, Software, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Data
736 Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Visualization. Samuel Leweke: Concep-
737 tualization, Methodology, Software, Writing - Review & Editing . Johannes
738 Schmölder: Methodology, Validation, Writing - Review & Editing. Gregor
739 Gassner: Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing. Eric von Lieres: Con-
740 ceptualization, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Project
741 Administration.

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Discretization			rapid-eq. binding		kinetic binding	
N_d	N_e^z	N_e^r	L^∞ error	L^∞ EOC	L^∞ error	L^∞ EOC
1	4	1	$1.591e-03$	—	$3.605e-03$	—
1	8	2	$5.511e-04$	1.53	$1.334e-03$	1.43
1	16	4	$1.885e-04$	1.55	$4.089e-04$	1.71
1	32	8	$5.480e-05$	1.78	$1.121e-04$	1.87
1	64	16	$1.461e-05$	1.91	$2.923e-05$	1.94
1	128	32	$3.762e-06$	1.96	$7.463e-06$	1.97
2	4	1	$2.199e-04$	—	$1.403e-04$	—
2	8	2	$5.853e-05$	1.91	$1.195e-05$	3.55
2	16	4	$4.513e-06$	3.70	$8.683e-07$	3.78
2	32	8	$1.405e-07$	5.00	$5.789e-08$	3.91
2	64	16	$8.818e-09$	3.99	$3.584e-09$	4.01
3	4	1	$3.053e-05$	—	$3.844e-06$	—
3	8	2	$4.054e-06$	2.91	$1.360e-07$	4.82
3	16	4	$1.192e-07$	5.09	$4.983e-09$	4.77
3	32	8	$2.269e-09$	5.72	$1.829e-10$	4.77
3	64	16	$5.148e-11$	5.46	$2.944e-11$	2.64
4	4	1	$3.559e-06$	—	$2.038e-07$	—
4	8	2	$1.618e-07$	4.46	$2.057e-09$	6.63
4	16	4	$8.575e-10$	7.56	$2.823e-11$	6.19
4	32	8	$1.549e-11$	5.79	$2.926e-12$	3.27

Table 1: Order-of-accuracy test results for the GRM with surface diffusion and linear binding, discretized according to the collocation DGSEM. Parameters are chosen according to Table S2.

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Figure 1: Jacobi matrix patterns for the interstitial transport discretization using exact integration DGSEM, collocation DGSEM and WENO FV. Here, we have $N_e = 10$ and $N_d = 3, 5$ and the number of WENO FV cells is respectively given by the resulting number of discrete points. The grid lines separate the degrees of freedom for DGSEM elements. Note that WENO FV is a subset of the DGSEM patterns and the collocation DGSEM pattern is a subset of the exact integration DGSEM pattern.

Figure 2: Benchmark for the collocation DGSEM (cDG) and exact integration DGSEM (DG) applied to a one-component LRM with rapid-equilibrium linear binding defined in Table S2. The spatial grid is gradually refined, starting with one element respectively.

Figure 3: Benchmark for a four-component LRMP with rapid-equilibrium SMA binding and parameters according to Table S3. The spatial grid is gradually refined, starting with four axial DGSEM elements and FV cells respectively.

Figure 4: Benchmark for a four-component GRM with (kinetic) SMA binding and parameters according to Table S3. The FV grid is refined as $N_e^z = 2^k$, $N_e^r = 2^{k-2}$, with $k \in \{5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, while the DG grid is refined for $N_d^z = 5$ as $N_e^z \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$, $N_e^r = 1$, $N_d^r \in \{1, 2, 6, 11\}$ and for $N_d^z = 4$ as $N_e^z \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$, $N_e^r = 1$, $N_d^r \in \{1, 2, 6, 8, 8, 11\}$, and for $N_d^z = 3$ as $N_e^z \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10\}$, $N_e^r = 1$, $N_d^r \in \{1, 1, 1, 2, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11\}$.

Figure 5: Benchmark for a four-component GRM with (kinetic) SMA binding with parameters according to Table S3. The spatial grid is gradually refined, starting with four axial and one radial DG element or FV cell respectively.

Figure 6: Outlet profile approximations for the DG ($N_d = 3$) and FV method with different spatial resolutions. The figure depicts the oscillatory DG behavior (upper row) and the dispersive WENO FV behavior (lower row) on the sharp concentration fronts of a LRM with Langmuir binding. Model parameters are chosen according to the “LRM2” value column in Table S1 (less dispersive setting).

Figure 7: Benchmarks for a less (left) and more (right) disperse two-component LRM with Langmuir binding. Parameters are chosen according to Table S1. The spatial grid is gradually refined, starting with 8 axial DG elements and 32 FV cells respectively.

Figure 8: Development of the largest negative values for a less (left) and more (right) disperse two-component LRM with Langmuir binding. Parameters are chosen according to Table S1. The spatial grid is gradually refined, starting with 8 axial DG elements and 32 FV cells respectively.